

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BAU	Business As Usual
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DR	Demand Response
DSM	Demand-Side Management
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EOL	End Of Life
ESS	Energy Storage Systems
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
PH	Peak Hour
PH-LCA	Peak-hourly Life Cycle Assessment
PSR	Pilot Site Responsible
PUC	Public Use Case
PV	Photovoltaic
ToU	Time-Of-Use
TSO	Transmission System Operator
V2B	Vehicle to Battery
V2G	Vehicle to Grid
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document is part of the WP3 (Exploitation), which main objectives are to define the exploitation activities of the INVADE Project, considering both economic (Stakeholders analysis, Business and Exploitation plan), and environmental aspects (Life Cycle Assessment). This document is the follow up of the previous deliverable D3.4, where the LCA methodology has been defined for each pilot site under the INVADE H2020 Project.

This report presents the final results of the task T3.7 for the project, updating the system boundaries if required, and calculating the environmental impacts and savings in terms of CO₂ emissions for each pilot-site, under the time horizon on where data have been collected.

Section 1 introduces the importance of sustainability and LCA on ICT and DERs technologies, for the decarbonization of the energy sector. Section 2 reviews the Life Cycle Assessment concept, defining the steps as well as the goal and scope for the INVADE H2020 Project. Section 3 describes all the assets that are placed in each pilot site and provides the environmental impact for each technology. It is important to notice that, in this section, a methodology to assess peak-hour electricity production is defined, enhancing the calculation of hourly environmental impacts and the implementation of DR considering not only economic saving but also environmental.

Later on, Section 4 updates and defines the pilot-sites case studies under the LCA tasks, after collecting the data from each pilot-site. Each case study considers the system boundaries for each pilot-site, as well as the assets placed and the available data, to calculate the environmental impacts under that time frame. The LCA methodology is then applied to calculate the potential environmental impacts of the Baseline Scenario (Scenario 1 or BAU), and the INVADE Scenario (Scenario 2). Each case study has its particular outcomes, comparing the environmental impacts of the two scenarios.

Finally, this deliverable presents the results for each case study, and compare them according to the obtained results. Section 5 describes them and includes good practices and insights for the development of DR activities.

The outcomes of this deliverable are input for WP9 (Business models) and WP10 (Pilots), which can enhance the development of flexibility strategies considering also the environmental impact of the DERs installation and operation.

This task has been performed by UPC in collaboration with VTT, who has expertise in LCA and sustainability. This task and deliverable are directly related to WP6 (Energy Storage Technologies), on which LCA for batteries is also important so as to consider the environmental impacts of batteries for stationery and flexibility activities.

1. Introduction

The protection of the environment is a real issue that is involving every day more people, but also companies, industries, and governments. Problems, like the increase in the global temperature and the pollution of air, water, and land, are the main obstacles that involve every person. In our everyday life, we make a lot of choices that can affect positively or negatively the problem. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), is a tool for analyzing the environmental impacts related to a certain product or process throughout its life cycle. Thus, LCA can tell us how much CO₂ has been emitted during the entire process of making a bottle of oil or it can also reveal how much fossil-based fuels have been used to manufacture a wind turbine. Anyway, regarding the INVADE project, LCA is used to look at the sustainability of technologies that are thought to replace the current ways of producing energy.

This document aims to provide the methodology according to standardized references as ISO 14040 and 14044 to assess the potential environmental impacts of the INVADE Project. This methodology has been defined in the previous deliverable D3.4 [4], and it is applied to the different pilot-sites, discussing the results in Section 4.

The increasing penetration of renewables energies into the global energy mix requires energy storage as well as other strategies to maximize the share of renewables. The unpredictability and intermittency of renewable sources is an obstacle to the development of the related technologies because a constant and secure supplying of electricity is a priority for the improvement of our energy systems. Through energy storage and other solutions like better management of the produced energy, increasing efficiency and the evolution of demand-response mechanisms, renewable power could become the only way to fulfill the energy requirements in the long term. This deliverable aims to demonstrate that this modern way of redesigning the energy systems is more environmentally friendly than the traditional ones.

Under this system, all pilot sites in Germany, Bulgaria, Norway, the Netherlands, and Spain are considered; as well as all the technologies that are implemented in each pilot site: PV Panels, EV chargers, Local controllers, Flexible Loads, distributed and centralized energy storage systems, and the electricity grid mixes. During the work performed for the development of the LCA, the communication with the pilot site responsible persons has been important to develop the models which serve as a basis for our analysis. Section 3 presents the devices that are located in the pilot site, the

scenarios to be considered, as well as the definition of the baseline and the INVADE scenario. After detailing the LCI of each pilot site, each technology is analyzed and then clustered if possible, between the different pilot sites. This facilitates the development of the task. Finally, conclusions are detailed in Section 5, showing the performed calculations and the outcomes related to the environmental impacts of the two scenarios. The final methodology is based on the references to KPIs included in deliverable D10.5 [1]. Every GHG pilot site analysis is related to one of its specific KPIs.

2. Life Cycle Assessment Concept

2.1. Definition

LCA, or Life Cycle Assessment, is a tool that enables evaluating the potential environmental impacts of a product during its entire lifetime, starting from a series of inputs and outputs related to the product itself. There are many intended use applications for an LCA such as a comparison of specific goods and services, monitoring environmental impacts of a product and even of an entire industry sector and greening the supply chain.

LCA is an effective tool also because it can perform a multi-media (air, water, waste, resource depletion, etc.) analysis and at the same time, the results cover multiple impacts (Global Warming Potential, Abiotic Depletion Potential, Acidification Potential, etc.). As already mentioned, ISO 14040, ISO 14044, and ISO 14067 are the standards considered for performing the LCA models [2], [3]. In *Figure 1*, a simple representation of the LCA structure is shown.

Figure 1 - Overview of an LCA process

2.2. Screening LCA

In the deliverable D3.4, a first calculation on the INVADE Life Cycle Assessment, also known as Screening LCA, was performed. It stands for defining the value chains and devices, calculation model and data collection.

According to ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, the four needed steps are Goal and Scope Definition, Life Cycle Inventory, Life Cycle Impact Assessment and Interpretation. The Goal and Scope of the INVADE LCA are extensively described in Table 1. For further information about the definition of the different parameters included in the INVADE Screening LCA, please refer to deliverable D3.4 [4].

Table 1: INVADE Project screening LCA description

INVADE Project Screening LCA		
GOAL	Intended application	Product evaluation, by assessing the potential environmental impacts of the cloud-based market platform for flexibility services in each pilot site.
	Purpose of the study	Provide the pilot operators and their value chain partners environmental information such as climate change impacts on their own energy system and devices. Identify and suggest a set of environmental indicators to be included in INVADE cloud-based platform.
	Intended audience	This analysis is going to be public. The target audiences of this assessment are the consortia partners, the pilot sites responsible persons, and the European Commission.

	Comparative analysis	Two different scenarios are considered for each pilot site: baseline and INVADE scenario. No comparison between pilots or different products (e.g. batteries) it is intended.
SCOPE	The function of the system	<p>The pilot systems consider energy production, distribution, and consumption.</p> <p>Each pilot site has the main purpose to implement the INVADE cloud-based platform for flexibility services, depending on the flexibility customer, according to deliverable D4.3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Congestion management (DSO) - Voltage/ Reactive Power control (DSO) - Controlled islanding (DSO) - Day-ahead portfolio optimization (BRP) - Intraday portfolio optimization (BRP) - Self-balancing portfolio optimization (BRP) - ToU optimization (Prosumer) - kWmax control (Prosumer) - Self-balancing (Prosumer) - Controlled islanding (Prosumer)
	Functional unit	1 kWh
	Reference flow	Energy flow (kWh), of electrical energy. It refers to energy provided by the pilots on a specified time period and it will be specified for each pilot in the next phase of the project.
	Description of the system	The INVADE pilot systems are based on DERs such as PV panels, Centralized Energy Storage (CES), Distributed Energy Storage (DES), One-way EV Chargers, bidirectional EV chargers
	System boundaries	<p>Screening LCA focuses on devices/energy products from the cradle to gate, i.e. no usage and disposal is included under the screening LCA.</p> <p>Later stages will consider the usage phase of the devices during the pilot tests. Regarding the batteries, cradle to grave will be considered.</p>
	Allocation procedures	Allocation methods are integrated into the life cycle inventory database datasets as mainly secondary data is used. For ecoinvent data, the “cut-off” system model has been chosen.
	Impact Assessment Method	CML 2015. Impact category to be assessed: GWP [kg CO ₂ eq/kWh]. Also known as Carbon footprint.
	Data requirements	<p>Primary data used from information provided by the pilot site responsible and from direct communication with manufacturers.</p> <p>Secondary data used from Literature and LCA specific Databases: GaBi, ecoinvent 3.1, and ENTSO-E TP</p>

3. Pilot Site Technologies

3.1. PV Panels

Photovoltaic panels are used in three out of five pilot sites (Germany, Bulgaria, and Norway). They are integrated with batteries to improve self-balancing and offer flexibility services (including congestion management and voltage/reactive power control). Different kinds of PVs is used in the pilot sites. They differ for manufacturing company, cell type and rated power (Table 2).

Table 2: Pilot-site PV panels types classification

Pilot Site	Manufacturer	PV panel MODEL	Cell Type	Rated Power per panel
Germany, badenova	Sharp	SH 165	Polycrystalline	10 kWp
	LC Solar	LC 130	Polycrystalline	11,52 kWp
	Sharp	SH 165	Polycrystalline	5,6 kWp
	Sharp	SH 120	Polycrystalline	2,8 kWp
	Solar World	Mono Black	Monocrystalline	17.1 kWp
	Yingli	YL-275	Monocrystalline	5.2 kWp
	Q-Cells	64-300WP	Monocrystalline	9.9 kWp
Bulgaria, Albena	Yingli Solar	Yingli YL275P-29b	Polycrystalline	27 kWp
Norway, Lyse	IBC Solar	N/A	Monocrystalline	2,9 kWp

In order to develop a fair LCA, an average model considering the common characteristics of the various solar panels should be developed. Usually, primary data regarding resources and energy used to manufacture and transport the modules are not directly shared from the manufacturers. In fact, it is also the case of the nine different PVs installed in the pilot sites. The conducted literature review turned out several papers that

used valuable and trustable data, so it was decided to take the results from a paper that has the closest characteristics to the pilot sites' PV panel.

Certain system boundaries have been set in advance to narrow down the development of the model. In fact, both the use phase and the disposal one are not considered because the INVADE project is planned to last just one year. The other constrictions to the model are derived from the literature review to understand the most important factors that impact the LCA.

Different studies have tried to review previous LCAs on photovoltaic modules to reduce the variability of the results and find common points from where to compare different analysis ([5], [6], [7], [8]). In fact, a recent review shows a range of values from a minimum of 32 g CO₂/kWh to a maximum of 88 g (considering the data from 2014) [5]. This study, as the previous ones, considers LCAs with different parameters (cell type, efficiency, performance ratio, solar irradiation, etc.).

Usually, the life cycle assessment for PV panels consider the entire life of the product, starting from the extraction of raw silicon until the disposal/recycling of the module. This last step has become important in recent years because of the environmental impacts related to the panel' waste and for the increasing available amount of data [9].

However, in our case, degradation of the modules and its lifetime were not taken into account, due to the scenario of one-year use-phase in the INVADE H2020 Project. Anyway, the most impactful step of the solar panel life is the manufacturing one [5], [10], [11], [12], [13]. As it is possible to see from *Figure 2*, the production of the module requires various energy-intensive steps, such as the solar grade silicon (SoG-Si) production [10] and the Solar grade multi-Si purification [13].

Figure 2: Life Cycle system boundaries of a multi-Si PV system. [14]

The cell can be manufactured resulting in two different technologies: Monocrystalline and polycrystalline. In the pilot sites, five polycrystalline and four monocrystalline PV types are installed. The first ones are usually manufactured with a lower silicon quality and therefore their efficiency is lower than the monocrystalline ones ([15], [16]). At the same time, the monocrystalline solar cells require more energy to be manufactured ([11], [17]). However, this distinction does not overly influence the difference in the final GWP, because of only two different processes in the manufacturing of ingots and wafer (CZ process and Directional Solidification for poly Wafer Process Diamond Wire Sawing and Slurry Wire Sawing for mono) ([5], [10]).

Solar panels cannot work without all the needed equipment like cables, inverters, switches and mounting systems. All these components together are called Balance of System (BOS) and they are essential for the PV functioning. Even if according to Fu et al. [13] it can be negligible for the LCA, other studies indicate that the inclusion of the BOS in the LCA can lead to an increase of certain factors up to 21%. ([8], [18], [19]). For example, looking at the possible type of installations onecoinvent database [20] (facade, flat-roof, slanted-roof), the results vary from 6301 to 8236 kg CO₂-eq/ unit.

Related to the overall process, in the work of Gazbour et al. [5], one of the outcomes is: results showed variability depending on the country where they are manufactured: carbon footprint results were lowest in Europe due to the lowest percentage share of the

fossil fuels in the electricity generation.” Considering that modules installed in Europe are produced at 78% in China, 14% in Europe and 6% in Asia & Pacific, the suggestion is to use a global electricity mix. Related to this, the transportation of the modules from the manufacturing location to the end-use site is rarely considered. Beloin et al. [21], prove that “In any studied case, the transportation between countries has a lower effect compared to the choice made on the source of electricity used during the different steps involved in the fabrication of modules for any technology.”

Another important aspect to look at in order to show a worthy LCA is the solar irradiation of the site in which the module is installed during the final use step. Using 1 kWh as functional unit, the energy produced is an outstanding factor that is clearly influenced by the quantity of power received from the sun in a certain area. For Southern European based locations, the suggested irradiation value is 1425 kW/m²/year [5]. Other parameters that affect the environmental impact of a PV panel are the performance ratio (relationship between the actual and theoretical energy outputs of the PV, suggested to be 81.8%) and the efficiency (the percentage of solar radiation which is transformed in electricity, 17.2% for monocrystalline and 16.3% for polycrystalline) [5].

For the INVADE project, only the GWP is calculated as the impact indicator.

Between all the analysed studies, the paper of Hou et al. [10] has been chosen as a reference paper because of the similarities with the pilot site technologies and the system boundaries, listed below.

- Functional Unit = 1 kWh
- Grid-connected PV generation
- Distributed PV systems
- Use of Chinese electricity grid mix
- Chinese PV technology data
- Manufacture, O&M and transmission phases
- Including BOS, transportation, and assembly
- 1 kW/m² as irradiance value

The results are equal to 72.14 kg CO₂-eq/ kWh for polycrystalline modules and 78.44 kg CO₂-eq/ kWh for the monocrystalline ones.

Table 3. GWP values from selected studies for PV panels

Polycrystalline modules	Monocrystalline modules
$72.14 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh	$78.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg CO ₂ -eq/ kWh

3.2. Batteries

All five INVADE pilot sites have stationary batteries: either residential batteries or larger stationary battery systems. The stationary batteries used in INVADE pilot sites are listed in *Table 7*, based on Deliverable D10.1 [22].

Regarding this specific technology, the LCA has the ultimate goal to assess the environmental impact of the different batteries' installation, rather than a cross-comparison. For the photovoltaic modules, the analysis is based on a literature review.

In order to identify the best literature sources available, a large selection of available data and studies were analysed. In the literature, there are LCA studies on several battery types. Following the needs of the INVADE pilots, only LIBs with NCM and LFP chemistries, as well as Redox-flow batteries, were analysed. No other types of batteries were studied. In the following, a brief overview of the battery technologies is given.

3.2.1. Li-ion batteries

Table 4 lists the GWP values of NCM batteries production retrieved from literature for comparison. The values are presented per kWh of the storage capacity of the battery and they demonstrate, that there is a wide variation in the results of the different studies.

Table 4. GWP values from selected studies for NCM batteries

Literature source	GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq/ kWh storage capacity]	LCA scope	Additional information
Ellingsen et al 2014 [23]	172 240-487	cradle-to-gate	The lower value gained under the optimal conditions, whereas the higher range reported depending on the amount of electricity consumed during the batteries production
Ambrose and Kendall 2016 [24]	254	cradle-to-gate	Mean GWP

Kim et al 2016 [25]	140	cradle-to-gate	
Majeau-Bettez et al., 2011 [26]	200	cradle-to-gate	
The US. EPA 2013 [27]	121	cradle-to-gate	producing 1kWh of storage capacity

When LIBs are used in stationary applications, they can be used to increase the utilization rate of renewable electricity produced from solar panels of wind farms and thus to reduce the impact of consuming grid electricity.

Recycling of batteries

There are multiple options for the recycling of LIBs. According to Zeng et al.[28], all LIBs recycling processes could be divided into mechanical, pyrometallurgical, hydrometallurgical, and biological. According to the authors, research on hydrometallurgical recycling of LIBs occupies 58% of all research activities in the field. During the process, LIBs are dismantled into different parts, and then metal-containing fractions are incinerated, and slag is leached with chemicals to selectively regain metals.

As with LIBs production, data on LIBs recycling is uncertain. The following values for the recycling of LIBs are listed in the table. The median GWP value from these sources identified was 16 ± 11 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh.

Table 5. GWP values from selected studies for LIBs

Literature source	GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq/ kWh]	LCA scope
Ellingsen et al 2016 [29]	8	recycling
Li et al 2014 [30]	27	recycling
US. EPA 2013 [31]	16-32	recycling

Remanufacturing

Besides recycling, the batteries can be refurbished to fulfill the needs of other applications, so-called second-life applications. This is particularly possible for the

batteries used in vehicles because they still have approximately 80% of their capacity at the end of their service. Usually, batteries that reached the end of their service lives are being transported to the remanufacturing facilities where they are inspected and tested to determine the SOH. If needed, the container, battery management system, and other auxiliary components of the batteries could be replaced. Due to their less-demanding use in stationary applications, the second-life BMS systems are smaller and lighter compared to an EV's BMS [32]. The energy consumption of the remanufacturing is estimated as the level of 27 kWh per battery check [33] or 4812 kWh for testing 4500 cells from EV LIB packs to build one stationary battery pack for 450 kWh energy storage [32].

3.2.2. Redox-flow batteries

In a redox flow battery (RFB) the energy storage and energy conversion function are separated. The liquid electrolytes are stored in tanks and pumped through stacks of battery cells, where the electrochemical reactions take place (*Figure 3*). Compared to other battery types, the possibility for spatial separation gives redox flow batteries the benefit that the stacks (determinant for the power rating of the battery) and the tanks (determinant for the storage capacity) can be dimensioned and tailored independently [34], [35]. This makes the RFBs very suitable for stationary large-scale storage systems. The RFBs are gaining growing attention, due to this flexible modular design and other benefits, such as long cycling life, active thermal management, and more ensured security [23].

Figure 3. Basic concept of vanadium redox flow battery.

Currently, the most promising RFB technology is vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFB), where vanadium is used in the electrolyte [35]. The advantage of VRFB is that the same

element can be used on both sides of the battery cell, which helps to avoid the cross-contamination of the electrolytes. In addition, the VRFBs have fast response and long cycle and service life, and they do not suffer from permanent self-discharge [35].

Weber et al [35] have made a detailed LCA study on the emissions of producing the VRFBs. Their results propose that the emissions of the production of VRFBs are mainly formed during the production of vanadium for the electrolyte, i.e. almost 90% of the total emissions are related to this production phase (*Figure 4*). Vanadium is usually produced from vanadium containing titanomagnetite ore. The main product is pig iron, and vanadium is concentrated in the slag from which it is recovered. The process requires high electricity inputs [35]. In their study, Weber et al. [35] have assumed that vanadium is produced in South Africa, where the electricity is mainly produced by coal. Therefore, the emissions of electricity used for vanadium production represent 46% of the total emissions of VRFB production. According to Ecoinvent 3.5 [36], the average high voltage electricity mix for South Africa has an emission factor of 1032 g CO₂-eq/kWh in 2014.

Figure 4. Illustration of the impact of the different production steps to the total emission of a VRFB. Data roughly estimated from Weber et al.[35].

Figure 5 illustrates the total emissions with possible other production sites with 30, 60, and 90% lower average emissions for electricity (around 720 gCO₂-eq/kWh, 410 g CO₂-eq/kWh, and 100 g CO₂-eq/kWh, respectively). In addition to South Africa, vanadium is produced in the US, Russia, China and some other countries such as Switzerland, Taiwan, Germany, and Brazil [31].

Figure 5: Illustration of the impact of 30, 60, and 90 % lower emissions for electricity production to the total emission. The original result, 38.2kgCO2-eq/MWh is from Weber et al.[35], and the total emission is estimated per MWh of electricity delivered by battery over the lifetime (20 years).

3.2.3. Values used in the LCA of the present study

As a result of the literature review, it was stated that the different batteries have such a wide variance in GWPs that it was not possible to use one average value for all the batteries like was done for the PVs. Despite there also being a fairly wide variance between different studies for individual technologies, it was decided to use an average value for each technology and apply that value to every pilot site individually (Table 6). For example, for Bulgaria, which just uses a centralized NMC 200kWh battery, 155 kg CO₂eq./kWh was applied. The values shown in Table 8 represent the greenhouse gas emissions per kWh battery storage capacity. These values also consider the production of the battery and are divide by its capacity.

Table 6. GWP values selected for the study. GWP¹ considers the entire life-time and the FU is for capacity, GWP² considers the FU for electricity stored

Pilot Site	Manufacturer	Model	Battery type	Average GWP ¹ [kgCO2eq/kWh]	Average GWP ² [kgCO2eq/kWh]	Energy Output	Additional information
Germany Badenova	Storion	StorE 20/120	Vanadium Redox	312	101.2 · 10 ⁻³	120 kWh	Centralized
	Sony	Olivine	LIB	161	70.6 · 10 ⁻³	9.2 kWh	Case 1 (decentralized)
	Enerwit	EnergyStore	LiFeYPO4	161	70.6 · 10 ⁻³	3.7 kWh	Case 2 (decentralized)
	LG Chem	Resu 10.0H	LIB	108	70.6 · 10 ⁻³	9.8 kWh	Case 3 (decentralized)
Spain Estabanell	Wattius	Tailor-made	LFP	161	77.6 · 10 ⁻³	210 kWh	Centralized

Bulgaria Albena	TesVolt	TS HV 70	NMC	155	$85.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	200 kWh	Centralized
Norway Lise	Eaton	N/A	LMO+NMC	105	$85.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	10 kWh	Decentralized
	Eaton	2nd life battery	LMO+NMC	105	$85.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	4.2 kWh	Decentralized
The Netherlands Greenflux Elaad NL	Samsung SDI	Alfen	NMC	155	$85.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	138 kWh	Centralized

According to [37], in order to consider the cycle lives of the different battery chemistries, the environmental impact per 1 kWh of storage capacity over the battery lifetime is calculated for all prior studies where information about the cycle life can be derived. On the contrary, Figure 6 shows the lifetime Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) and GWP given in the reviewed studies, being per kWh of storage capacity over the whole battery lifetime. These values are the ones considered for the development of the LCA model for each pilot-site since the GWP value is calculated using 1 kWh of stored electricity. Thus, using batteries make sense if the emission from electricity production is higher than 25-93.3 g/kWh, depending on the battery type.

As an example, averaged over all LIB batteries, providing 1 kWh of electricity can lead to a GWP impact of 74 g CO₂-eq only due to the production of the battery, without considering internal inefficiencies. If internal inefficiencies are also taken into consideration, as highlighted by Peters et al. [37], for storing 1 kWh the corresponding GWP is 46.7 g CO₂-eq, considering the average European electricity grid mix.

Figure 6: Lifetime CED and GWP given in the reviewed studies for the different battery chemistries

3.3. EV chargers

The Electric Vehicle chargers are certainly the newest technology, which will be analyzed for this project. In fact, not so many LCA studies have been performed on this product and the current literature is limited to certain countries and limited by specific constraints (annual distance driven, distance between charging stations and number of vehicles per station). Another problem is that there are no commonly accepted standards for the charging infrastructure density, making it even more difficult to deploy an effective LCA for this specific product. Even if the most LCAs of electrical vehicles neglect the impact related to the energy supply infrastructure, it has been demonstrated that it can be a relevant factor [38], contributing up to 8% of the overall EV LCA [39].

In this project, there are two locations including EV chargers in their Pilot Use Cases (PUCs), Norway and the Netherlands. These two countries are respectively the first and the third in the World in terms of market share in 2019 (30% sale share in Norway, 9.7% in the Netherlands) [40], and an increase of 6.8% EVs sales in 2019 in the Netherlands [41].

Table 7: EV chargers and controllers' description

Pilot Site	Manufacturer	Model	AC Rated Power	One-way/ Smart / V2G
The Netherlands, Elaad NL	Alfen	EVE Mini	7.2 kW	One-way
The Netherlands, Elaad NL	Greenflux	Smart Charging Controller	10 W	Smart
Norway, Lise	Schneider	EVlink smart wallbox	11 kW	One-Way

The main EV chargers considered are the AC-EV chargers, that only consider one way of energy flow, which means, charging the EV. Later on, smart controllers such as the ones implemented in the Dutch pilot site permit the implementation of demand-side management activities such as controlling the charging process of the EV considering the energy prices for ToU optimization.

Following the adopted LCA models for PVs and batteries for evaluating the environmental impacts of the EV chargers, values from the literature are considered. Usually, the EV charging infrastructure is compared with conventional or developing technologies. This is the case studied in [38], where electrical infrastructures in Portugal, France, and the USA are compared with hydrogen-based systems, showing how the different electricity grid mixes influence the final results. The same approach is performed in [39], but comparing gasoline and diesel charging point's network with the electrical vehicles one in Portugal. The conclusion of the study case is that: "The electric vehicle energy supply infrastructures are more carbon and energy-intensive per MJ of supplied fuel than conventional ones". Another comparison is presented in [42], where plug-in and wireless charging are evaluated through the greenhouse gas emission factor, resulting in similar outcomes. These values could even be higher if the efficiency of wireless systems will reach the same as the plug-in ones. The other two studies are focused on solar-powered charging stations [43], [44] leading to higher GWP outcomes, regarding the infrastructure itself, because of the PV manufacturing process contribution.

A pertinent study about EV chargers is written by Lucas et al. [40]. It defines an assessment methodology through eight different indicators (carbon footprint included) to allow a comparison among EV charging infrastructures, delivering a mean result in kg CO_{2eq}/MJ, easily transformable in kg CO_{2eq}/kWh. Furthermore, the data are derived from a database owned by Elaad, the company in charge of the procedures in the Dutch pilot

site. Considering only standard three-phase charging stations with a maximum output power of 12 kW and considering a 10 years lifetime, the mean value for the GWP is equal to 4.44 g CO_{2eq}/kWh, being the min and the max respectively 2,09 and 10.65 g CO_{2eq}/kWh. The main problem to solve according to the authors is the low energy use ratio in comparison with the high availability of electricity, meaning the charging stations are less exploited than what would be needed to affect positively in terms of energy consumption. This fact should be taken into consideration to not risk of obtaining higher environmental impacts than desired.

Table 8: EV charging station GWP used for the INVADE case, considering the manufacturing

EV charging stations GWP
15.7 · 10 ⁻³ kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh

3.4. Electricity production (grid mixes)

The INVADE LCA needs to take into account the different assets installed (PV Panels, EV chargers, Local controllers, Flexible Loads, but mainly distributed and centralized energy storage systems). Besides that, all the different pilot projects sites have in common the fact they are connected to their country's electricity grid. In order to develop an analysis, which is in line with the LCA methodology, the pollutants emitted to produce electricity should be taken into consideration. The overall aim in many pilots is shaving the electricity peaks during hours of higher consumption to obtain a more flattened energy curve, moving consumption periods to off-peak hours or where DERs have their maximum production. The time dependence of the environmental impacts related to electricity production is relevant for the INVADE goals. Thanks to the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform, an online data platform for European electricity system data, established through the Regulation (EU) No. 543/20131, the hourly electricity production data from different sources of the five targeted countries is obtained. The total production by resource is environmentally assessed using specialized software, GaBi. An explanation of the methodology followed to obtain the national electricity production GWPs is presented in the following section.

As explained in Section 2, certain system boundaries are set to narrow the analysis on the wanted outcomes. For example, the functional unit has to give a good qualitative and quantitative description of the process. The functional unit was set to 1 kWh of electricity

produced. Thanks to this approach, different amounts of generation are compared observing the relative environmental impacts. The more electricity is produced, the more GHG is emitted. Hence, the GHG emissions can be calculated corresponding to every kWh generated by the grid as a kilogram of CO₂eq./kWh.

The system boundaries limit the LCA framework by establishing resource inputs and emissions outputs of the system, excluding those that are out of the LCA scope. Elements such as grid losses, import/export, power plant's own consumption, and allocation procedures are described below.

Specifically, in this LCA, the background system regards all the previous steps of the final electricity production process (e.g. the extraction of the fuel, the refinement, its transportation to the power plant) while the foreground system is related to the effective production of 1 kWh inside the power plant. For the background system, the used dataset includes imported electricity from neighbouring countries and transmission/distribution losses (e.g. the electricity mix of the country which exports the fuel, the losses in the transportation, etc). However, the GaBi Professional Software used for this task, the system does not include the same values, meaning that it does not contain the exports of the produced electricity in other countries, the imports of electricity from bordering nations and the grid losses to distribute the produced electricity [45]. This is why grid losses (distribution, transmission) of the targeted countries are not considered in the model.

Another subject of discussion is the importation and exportation amount of electricity from neighbouring countries. In the ENTSO-E TP, the classification named "Actual Generation per Production Type" includes the natural resources used for electricity production. It means that the amount of fuels utilized includes the import of these substances from other countries. On the contrary, it does not include the already produced electricity imports between bordering countries. This last specific data is integrated into a different class, "Cross-border physical flows", not taken into account in the study. In fact, incorporating electricity imports and exports of electricity in a national grid mix could lead to inaccuracy and imprecision, when dealing with GWP calculations, due to the fact it is not possible to know from which power plants the electricity comes from.

Regarding power plants' own electricity consumption values, they are taken from official statistics of IEA (International Energy Agency) through the used software tool and so

they are included in the model [46]. Specifically, own consumption to pump up the water in hydro pumped storage power plants is considered when data from TP are available.

Finding the suitable allocation factor might be sometimes problematic and it can lead to significant impacts on the LCA results. Whenever it is possible, allocation should be avoided, according to [2]. Combined heat and power plants (CHP) produce two outputs and so it is needed to allocate the environmental impacts of just electricity production. GaBi software presents a database for every resource used in CHP power plants as natural gas, biogas, heavy fuel oil, hard coal, lignite, and biomass. In the database, there are data regarding the share of electricity, the overall efficiency and the share of electricity to thermal energy within a CHP plant. According to the description of the used dataset, for the combined heat and power production, allocation by energetic content is considered.

To develop the GHG emission assessment model, based on the LCA framework and considering both peak and off-peak hours from the ENTSO-E TP, the methodology presented in

Figure 7: Methodology for PH-LCA on electricity production

is applied. The methodology followed for this study is based on the identification of electricity production peak hours for every day of the year, compared to the baseload. Every single peak hour, extracted from a statistical source, was analysed to define the resources used to meet the greatest electricity demand of the day. The electricity mix was normalized into the functional unit of 1 kWh. Then, the resultant GHG emissions, and therefore the GWP impact indicator values, were calculated. To compare the obtained results for peak-hours to average values, the traditional LCA approach was also implemented. In this case, all the hours of the year 2018 were considered. Accordingly, peak hours GWP values were compared with the average, resulting in monthly results to highlight the seasonal variations.

Figure 7: Methodology for PH-LCA on electricity production

The scope of this comparison is based on highlighting the differences in the use of various resources to meet the electricity demand in different time frames. A similar approach is followed in [47]–[49], but the results are presented in order to show the link between electricity demand and carbon intensity and not to compare peak hour values with a fixed average. In [50], the aim is to determine the hourly time slot where the highest CO₂ intensity takes place throughout the year. This approach may hide the seasonality between summer and winter since the peak hour time slot differs from season to season. In this paper, the hourly analysis enhances the differentiation of GHG emissions from peak hours and off-peak hours.

This paper bases its results on the data extracted from the Transparency Platform (TP) of the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E),

as well as the GaBi Software database. The software allows the carbon intensity of every source to be assessed, considering the electricity produced as input. The related database is essential to differentiate the impact of each technology in different nations, having variable country-based data in which the same power plant can have different emission factors according to the country in which it is based.

The plots showing the results of the peak hours' monthly analysis compared to the yearly average are presented in Section 0, where they are related to the country of belonging. To give a first overview of which are the environmental impacts related to the different resources used, Table 9 is extracted from [51], and it shows that renewable energies have a non-zero GWP value.

Table 9: Emission factors of power production technologies

Energy source	GWP [kg CO ₂ / kWh]
Hard coal	0.66-1.05
Lignite	0.8-1.3
Natural gas	0.38-1.0
Oil	0.53-0.9
Nuclear	0.003-0.0035
Biomass	0.008-0.13
Hydropower	0.002-0.02
Solar	0.013-0.19
Wind	0.003-0.041

Table 10 summarizes the results obtained with the traditional LCA and PH-LCA approaches in each specific country. Countries with a consistent share of flexible hydropower in their capacity portfolios such as Bulgaria, Norway and Spain mainly used this resource to meet the peak hours' demand because of its rapidity in producing electricity and its low marginal cost. As a result, lower GWP figures were obtained compared to the yearly average. During the months in which the GWP was higher than the comparable value, it was demonstrated that the more conventional power plants

were powered to reach the demand during the spikes of production, because of nationwide lack in rainfall and water shortages. Germany and the Netherlands mainly had their peak hours production during times in which wind and/or solar power were efficiently running, also leading to lower GWP values. Particularly in Germany, the good alternation of sunny and windy days, the first ones during the summer months and the second ones during winter were advantageous for the national electricity grid. Regarding the Netherlands, the almost constant usage of natural gas to match the national electricity request throughout the year did not lead to substantial changes in the monthly GWP values.

Table 10: Summary of results between LCA and PH-LCA

Approach	Country / Indicator	Bulgaria [kg CO2/kWh]	Germany [kg CO2/kWh]	The Netherlands [kg CO2/kWh]	Norway [kg CO2/kWh]	Spain [kg CO2/kWh]
<i>Traditional</i>	Yearly average GWP	0.617	0.476 <i>(National)</i> 0.139 <i>(Badenova)</i>	0.287	0.0287	0.281
<i>Attributional PH-LCA</i>	Minimum GWP on PH (month)	0.397 <i>(April)</i>	0.362 <i>(April)</i>	0.256 <i>(April)</i>	0.0172 <i>(August)</i>	0.157 <i>(March)</i>
	Maximum GWP on PH (month)	0.717 <i>(October)</i>	0.502 <i>(February)</i>	0.303 <i>(August)</i>	0.0335 <i>(May)</i>	0.341 <i>(September)</i> <i>(November)</i>
	PH Resources	<i>Lignite</i> <i>Hydro</i>	<i>Solar, Lignite,</i> <i>Wind</i>	<i>Natural gas</i> <i>Solar</i> <i>Wind</i>	<i>Hydro</i> <i>Natural gas</i>	<i>Wind</i> <i>Natural gas</i> <i>Hydro</i>
	Average - PH difference [%]	-35.7% +16.21%	-23.9% +5.2%	-10.9% +5.6%	-40.1% +16.7%	-44.2% +21.3%

4. Pilot Sites Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The INVADE Project is based on five pilot-sites located in five countries: Bulgaria, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway, and Spain. All the pilot-sites are implemented to develop different use cases to prove the cloud-based flexibility management platform. The main goal is to provide and use flexibility services for several purposes such as congestion management, load shifting, and voltage/reactive power control, for instance. Alongside this Section, the main specs of each pilot site are presented, as well as the LCA classification and characterization steps, leading to the final results specifically related to each pilot. In the following subsection, two figures per pilot-site are presented, to represent the two scenarios considered for each pilot site. The approach for each pilot site is, as defined previously, from cradle to gate.

4.1. System boundaries

The LCA work is split into different tasks, depending on the elements to assess and the technologies involved. As already explained, not all the pilot sites involved all the different technologies. Figure 8 shows the general scheme of the pilot-site LCA. In Section 0, for each pilot site, two figures are presented, one referred to the BASE scenario and the other one to the INVADE scenario. Furthermore, every pilot site has its own KPIs to test and for the purpose of this deliverable, the KPI that expresses an environmental impact of the pilot itself has been related to the LCA analysis.

Figure 8: General scheme of the devices considered in the INVADE LCA.

4.2. Pilot sites

4.2.1. Norwegian Pilot Site

According to Deliverable D10.5 [1], the Norwegian pilot investigates and demonstrates the intersection between V2H/loads/PV, effect-based tariffs and energy management in private homes and buildings, and how they are combined in new business models. The pilot is split into different categories, with different goals. The LCA analysis is based on a specific sub-pilot, which includes an average household model with PV panels, ESS and EV chargers.

Figure 9: Norwegian Pilot-Site Baseline system boundaries.

With the implementation of the INVADE platform (Figure 10), the desired achievements are related to optimal consumption of self-produced solar power and power management throughout the day to get the lowest possible power bill for the end customer. The energy-efficient components will affect the environmental impacts of the pilot site as well. KPI number 3 is related to the LCA analysis of the Norwegian pilot site, as shown in Table 11.

Figure 10: Norwegian Pilot-Site INVADE system boundaries.

Table 11: KPI for the Norwegian pilot-site

Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Definition
Optimize utilization of self-produced energy.	To test different set-ups of battery / flexible loads, for self-balancing vs feed-in to the grid.

As can be stated from the KPI shown above, the main objective of the implementation of the INVADE platform is to lower the electricity bill for the end-user, by increasing the household self-produced energy. Despite, usually decreasing electricity bill by developing local ecosystems can also lead to lower environmental impacts. However, when implementing local ecosystems with DERs, the national electricity grid mix should be considered, in order to decrease the already existing environmental impacts. Usually, countries with a high carbon intensity of the electricity grid can achieve high potential reductions, associated with the use of coal or natural gas.

4.2.1.1. Scenario 1: Grid mix usage

Norway has a very particular energy grid mix, as shown in *Table 12*. The main used resource is hydro, accounting for nearly 95% of the total electricity production for 2018.

Table 12: Percentage of resources used in Norway

Hydro	Wind onshore	Natural gas	Others
94.8 %	2.32 %	2.10 %	0.77 %

Using this electricity grid mix to assess its environmental impact, the carbon intensity or GWP value accounts for 0.0287 kg CO₂-eq/kWh. This value is significantly lower than in other countries, as Spain or Bulgaria, on which the GWP value accounts for 0.281 kg CO₂-eq/kWh and 0.617 kg CO₂-eq/kWh, respectively.

4.2.1.2. Scenario 2: DERs installation and usage

Considering the environmental impacts of DERs,

	Electricity production GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh]	PV panels [kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh]	EV Chargers [kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh]	DES/CES [kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh]
Scenario 1: grid	0.0287	-	-	-
Scenario 2: DERs	0.0287	0.07844	0.0157	0.0856

In this case, there are no potential benefits for Norwegian households implementing DERs, since the environmental impacts of manufacturing, using, recycling and disposing of them outweigh the impact of the electricity production in Norway, of 95% Hydro. Hence, in this case, the implementation of DERs might lead to a greater environmental impact of electricity production.

4.2.2. Dutch Pilot Site

The sub-pilots located in the Netherlands aim to analyse the impact of a large-scale implementation of EVs charging on the electricity network, and how they can be operated to achieve economic savings, a greater share of renewables, and to avoid the upgrading of the electrical network. In the Dutch pilot site, two different entities are operating: GreenFlux is aiming to use the developed Smart Charging features and tools in

commercial offerings. Elaad wants to study the impact on the grid from a DSO perspective. There are four sub-pilots, considering households, large offices and parking, small public offices and large public charging points across the Netherlands. For the purpose of the LCA task, a general life cycle assessment model analyzing the environmental benefits from the implementation of EV chargers and EV smart charging controllers is developed.

The focus of the Dutch pilot site is on the impact of electric vehicle charging on the electricity network and the possibility to use as much as possible renewable energy, meanwhile keeping the energy grid in balance, according to D10.5 [1]. KPI number 1 is further analysed from an environmental perspective.

Key Performance Indicator	Definition
The share of renewable energy	To show the improvement in the share of renewable energy

Figure 11 details the baseline scenario, where there are already EVs on the streets and EV chargers installed. The energy consumption comes from the main electricity grid mix in the Netherlands.

Figure 11: Dutch Pilot-Site Baseline system boundaries.

Figure 12 details the system boundaries for the INVADE scenario, where the EV smart charging controller and the Cloud Platform have been installed to control the EV charging process to achieve the pilot-site objectives: congestion management and voltage control

alongside the distribution network; ToU optimization and self-balancing by using renewable energy as PV panels.

Figure 12: Dutch Pilot-Site INVADE Scenario system boundaries.

Using average values from the Dutch pilot-site, public chargers consume 2,200 kWh per year, while private chargers consume 3,500 kWh per year. By using these values, environmental savings can be quantified depending on the scenario.

4.2.2.1. Scenario 1: EV charging using the electricity grid mix

Data from ENTSO-E TP for 2018 of the electricity production in the Netherlands has been collected. The share of resources for 2018 is shown in Table 13:

Table 13: Share of resources in the Netherlands for 2018 [52]

Natural gas	Wind	Nuclear	Solar	Biomass
67.85 %	19.48 %	6.61 %	5.48 %	0.58 %

Mainly, the electricity supply is covered by natural gas, followed by wind power, nuclear and solar PV. The average GWP value for the electricity supply in 2018 has been of 0.287 kg CO₂eq /kWh. However, this GWP value can vary when the EV is charged during high demand time-periods, as shown in Table 14:

Table 14: Summary of results for Scenario 1: grid consumption

	Grid mix GWP [kg CO2-eq]	EV charging [kWh/year]	Total emissions [kg CO2-eq]
Public chargers: average values	0.287	2,200	631.4
Public chargers: Peak hours	0.303	2,200	666.6
Private chargers: average	0.287	3,500	1,004.5
Private chargers: Peak hours	0.303	3,500	1,060.5

4.2.2.2. Scenario 2: EV charging using the INVADE Platform

There is no difference in total energy consumption as the demand is the same. However, the same amount of energy is delivered at different time-periods and with different power rated. By using the INVADE Platform, the PV panels already located in the pilot-site are operated by implementing optimization models and maximizing the share of renewables, also according to the KPI already defined. The Dutch pilot-site states in D10.6 [53] that, by using the INVADE concept, a greater share of renewables is achieved. On average, this increase is 7%, being on specific cases up to 23%. As a result, the EV charging process was nearly 100% done using DERs.

The implementation of the INVADE platform leads to an increase in the share of renewables, proving the KPI stated above. The cloud platform is an effective way of managing the demand-side according to the generation from local renewable sources, PV in this case. Since the Netherlands is a country that relies on fossil fuels to cover the baseline and peak hours, it is important to use DERs to lower the environmental impact of the EV charging process.

As highlighted in Table 15, by using PV panels, there is no need to consider peak and off-peak hours, since the environmental impact of the PV panel remains the same. On the contrary, there is a need to optimize and schedule the charging process of the EV

when there is a power injection coming from the PV panels, maximizing the use of PV power instead of the grid.

Table 15: Summary of results for Scenario 2: INVADE platform

	PV GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq]	EV charging [kWh/year]	Total emissions [kg CO ₂ -eq]
Public chargers	0.07214	2,200	158.708
Private chargers	0.07214	3,500	252.49

Furthermore, by implementing the INVADE concept, the upgrade of the electrical network can be avoided. This is also a key factor for the decarbonization of the electricity sector, as well as for lowering the environmental impact of the electricity supply. The expansion of 500 km of the electrical network, considering the clearing of the surroundings, the raw materials, as well as the manufacturing process, would represent an environmental impact of 350,000.00 kg CO₂-eq/kWh [54]. As a summary, and as shown in **Table 16**, with the implementation of Scenario 2, average CO₂ reductions of 74,8% can be achieved for public and private chargers.

Table 16: Summary of results for the Dutch Pilot-site

		Total emissions [kg CO ₂ -eq/year]
Scenario 1	Public chargers: AVG	631.4
	Public chargers: PH	666.6
	Private chargers: AVG	1,004.5
	Private chargers: PH	1,060.5
Scenario 2	Public chargers	158.708
	Private chargers	252.49

4.2.3. Bulgarian Pilot Site

The pilot in Albena, Bulgaria, demonstrates how centralized battery storage, combined with PV panels, can contribute to the overall energy efficiency of a large number of consumers.

Figure 13 represents the baseline system boundaries for the Bulgarian pilot-site. There, the model contains hotel consumption that is supplied from the main electricity grid.

Figure 13: Bulgarian Pilot-Site Baseline system boundaries.

Figure 14 depicts the system boundaries for the Bulgarian pilot-site under the INVADE scenario. PV panels are installed together with a first-life centralized energy storage unit to increase the share of the DERs installed in the pilot-site. By doing this, they can provide 3 types of flexibility services. From the BRP point of view: self-balancing portfolio optimization; and from the prosumer perspective, kW_{MAX} control and self-balancing.

Figure 14: Bulgarian Pilot-Site INVADE Scenario system boundaries

The LCA of the Bulgarian pilot site is focused on seeing the differences in CO₂ emissions before and after the implementation of solar panels and centralized battery.

According to deliverables D10.2 and D10.5, the Key Performance Indicators for the Bulgarian Pilot site are based on increasing the share of renewables on the total pilot consumption and increasing the economic savings due to local generation from PV and batteries.

Key Performance Indicator	Definition
The share of renewable energy (SoRE)	To show the improvement in the share of renewable energy 100* Volume of RE/Total Volume of Energy [%]
Cost savings from increased RES share	Cost savings due to decreased delivery energy because of local generation

However, for the purpose of this deliverable, the aim is to calculate the environmental savings due to local generation, provided by PV panels and CES. In this case, the water boilers are not considered in the model since they are used as thermal storage and no data have been collected for this time period.

The available data for the LCA covers one month of study, starting in September 2019. The main purpose of the Bulgarian pilot site is to decrease the overall energy supply costs. For this reason, PV panels and batteries have been installed. First, to decrease electricity consumption directly from the grid. Secondly, to use the batteries to be charged when electricity market prices are low and discharge them for the hotel consumption when prices are high, on peak-demand time periods.

The electricity energy mix of Bulgaria is deeply still focused on fossil fuel with 42.5 % of energy which comes from lignite and on nuclear power plants, which produces around 35 % of the total electricity. The most important renewable energy sources present on the mix are hydropower with a sharing of 11.5 %, while PVs and wind are still under 3 %.

Due to the really low sharing of renewables, this study wants to highlight the improvement in terms of reduction of CO₂ emissions by integrating PV panels and batteries.

The pilot site has a total monthly consumption (September-October 2019) equal to 178,917.619 kWh. Thanks to the installation of 27 kW of PVs panels, part of the energy

consumption does not come from the Bulgarian grid mix, but directly from solar energy. Due to the fact that the average emission factor of the Bulgarian electricity mix is quite high, it is expected a deep reduction in the amount of CO₂ emitted.

Moreover, a 200kWh battery installed in the pilot-site allows reducing the energy required during peak hours. This could be really effective in terms of GWP reduction. Indeed, Bulgaria shows a higher value of CO₂ emission during peak hours. Regarding this, it is important to notice that the resources used to cover peak hours, in the case of Bulgaria, are mainly lignite and hydro. Hence, environmental savings can be achieved by using the batteries to be charged during off-peak hours.

4.2.3.1. Scenario 1: Baseline

The first scenario considers the amount of CO₂ emitted to produce the energy consumed by the hotel in a month, 178,917.619 kWh. Considering the average emission factor of the Bulgarian electricity production, calculated in Section 3.4, it is possible to quantify the total amount of CO₂ produced by the pilot-site.

$$178,917.619[\text{kWh}] * 0.617 \left[\frac{\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq}}}{\text{kWh}} \right] = 110,392.171 \text{ kg } \text{CO}_2 \text{ eq}$$

4.2.3.2. Scenario 2: Installation of PV panels

total energy consumed [kWh]	178,917.619
PV generated [kWh]	2,407.524
share of PV after the implementation of the INVADE Platform from the total consumed energy [%]	1.35%

Thanks to the installation of polycrystalline PV panels, the total energy production of 2,407.524 kWh is achieved. Knowing that the emission factor from PV production, considering the entire life cycle, is equal to 0.07214 $\frac{\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq}}}{\text{kWh}}$ it is possible to calculate the new amount of CO₂ emitted by the pilot-site.

$$\begin{aligned} (178,917.619 - 2,407.524)[\text{kWh}] * 0.617 \left[\frac{\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq}}}{\text{kWh}} \right] + 0.07214 \left[\frac{\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq}}}{\text{kWh}} \right] * 2,407.524[\text{kWh}] = \\ = 109,080.407 \text{ kg } \text{CO}_2 \text{ eq} \end{aligned}$$

Comparing the results obtained it is possible to observe that the use of PVs panels leads to a decrease of CO₂ emissions, although the PV share only accounts for 1.37 % of the total energy consumption.

4.2.3.3. Scenario 3: PV panels and CES

Table 17: Overall collected data from Albena Pilot-Site

Total energy consumed [kWh]	178,917.619
PV generated [kWh]	2,407.524
Share of PV after the implementation of the INVADE Platform from the total consumed energy [%]	1.35%
Battery discharging energy total [kWh]	2,801.739
Share of Battery after the implementation of the INVADE Platform from the total consumed energy [%]	1.57%

In this third scenario, the entire pilot-site assets are taken into account, both PV panels and CES. Especially, in this case, the aim to highlight the effectiveness of the introduction of a CES. In this scenario, the CES is charged during off-peak hours and discharged during peak-hours. Hence, a new emission factor should be calculated for off-peak hours, when the CES is charged. This factor is calculated using data from ENTSOE TP, according to the share of resources used during off-peak hours between the month of study, and it is equal to 0.402 kg CO₂ eq /kWh. As it is possible to observe, it is lower than the average Bulgarian emission factor. This is due to the fact that Bulgaria uses mainly nuclear and hydro a part from lignite during off-peak hours.

- a. Environmental impact due to electricity consumption

$$(TOT_{kWh} - Charging_{kWh}) * 0,617 = 107,178.056 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{eq}$$

- b. Environmental impact of PV electricity production

$$ElectricityProduction_{PV} \cdot GWP_{PV} = 2407,524 * 0,07214 = 173.679 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{eq}$$

- c. Environmental impact due to charging the battery during off-peak hours and discharging it during peak-hours.

$$Charging_{kWh} * 0.502 = 2,801.739 * 0.402 = 1,126.299 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{eq}$$

- d. Environmental impact of battery manufacturing and internal inefficiencies.

Battery contribution to CO₂ emissions is related to two different factors: one depends on the lifetime specific energy and depends on the type and on the size of the battery, while the other one depends on the internal inefficiency of the battery. It is assumed the internal efficiency of the battery equal to 90 % and, knowing that the energy-charged it is equal to 2801.739 kWh and that each 1 kWh of energy stored correspond to 0.0467 g_{CO₂} emitted [37].

$$2801.739 \text{ kWh} * \frac{0.0476 [\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}]}{1 [\text{kWh}]} = 130.841 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$$

While the emissions related to the electricity stored are equal to [37]:

$$2801.739 \text{ kWh} * 0.0856 \left[\frac{\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}}{\text{kWh}} \right] = 239.83 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$$

Because it depends only on the size of the battery. As a result, the total amount of emissions related to the installation and use of the battery is equal to 147.961 kg of CO₂-eq. Hence, the overall emissions in the third scenario are equal to 108,847.705 kg of CO₂-eq.

As it is possible to appreciate from *Table 18*, a reduction in the overall emission of CO₂ is achieved by implementing the INVADE platform under one month of study. Moreover, the integration of battery allows managing the demand side strategy in order to reduce the demand during peak hours and consequently the use of Lignite.

Table 18: Results Summary of Bulgarian Pilot-site

	Grid mix [kWh]	PV [kWh]	CES [kWh]	kg CO ₂ -eq
Scenario 1	178,917.619	-	-	110,392.171
Scenario 2	176,510.095	2,407.524	-	109,080.407
Scenario 3	173,708.356	2,407.524	2,801.739	108,847.705

4.2.4. Spanish Pilot Site

The pilot-site is located in Granollers, Catalonia. It is focused on the integration of Centralised Energy Storage (CES) in the MV grid to prevent and mitigate congestions in the MV distribution network and the power transformer located there. This CES unit is going to provide flexibility services to this purpose, by means of the INVADE platform. There are two main objectives in this pilot-site (DSO side) and balancing (BRP side). First, to continuously supply electricity to a critical building and ensure its functionalities. Secondly, to develop congestion management activities to ensure the correct operation of the pilot site network.

Figure 15 shows the Pilot-Site system boundaries under a baseline scenario. In this case, the pilot consumption is supplied by means of the Estabanell distribution network.

Figure 15: Spanish Pilot-Site system boundaries

Figure 16 shows the INVADE scenario, where the CES unit is installed together by a power electronics device (PED), to integrate the CES to the MV distribution network. By implementing the INVADE platform, the CES and the PED, four flexibility services can be provided. From the BRP perspective, the self-balancing portfolio optimization can be implemented and reduce and/or avoid deviation penalties. In terms of the DSO, congestion management, voltage, and reactive control and controlled islanding actions can be performed.

Figure 16: Spanish Pilot-Site INVADE Scenario system boundaries

For the purpose of this task, just the role of the battery to provide continuous operation mode to the critical building is analysed. The large-scale battery focus is on replacing the diesel generator previously used as backup support for a critical building. One of the pilot site KPIs is chosen and related to the LCA analysis (KPI number 7, from deliverable D10.5 [1]).

Key Performance Indicator	Definition
Optimization Diesel Generation	quantity (in kg) of CO ₂ emissions avoided in the current scenario, compared with the diesel generator previously used to offer controlled islanding to the DSO control center

The pilot site responsible persons decide to develop this KPI with a strong hypothesis: all the energy that comes from the electricity grid has a GWP equals to 0, because it is produced by renewable energies. But, as depicted from Table 5, even renewable sources have an environmental impact in terms of CO₂ emissions, and this is why the analysis will be performed taking into account the Spanish electricity grid mix. In this scenario, the battery is not charged and discharged according to the market price to avoid high prices time-periods. Hence, the average value for GWP emissions will be considered.

Spain can count different resources that have a high share of electricity production, like Germany. Natural gas and hard coal are fossil fuels more used, with percentages of 20.91% and 13.29% respectively. Nuclear power plants account for 22.46% of the total yearly electricity production and wind onshore power represents a consistent share (20.21%). Solar production is present also during night hours because of some Concentrated Solar Power plants with molten salts.

The highest amount of power produced during peak hours is in February, March, and November, while the months with the lowest request during peak times are April, May, and June.

Figure 17: Monthly peak hours GWP compared with average through the year (dotted line) in Spain

As depicted from Figure 17, the high-power production during peak hours is well related to the high values of the GWP. The same can be said for the months with lower values than the average. Depending on when the diesel generator intervenes to power the critical building, the electricity grid mix can give different values of GWP when substituting it.

From the data shared by the Spanish pilot site, the diesel generator was used on three different occasions during 2018:

1. To verify its right operation: two times per year, 15 minutes each
2. Planned operation: 120 minutes
3. Incidence on LV and/or MV network: two times in the year, 30 minutes each

4.2.4.1. Scenario 1: Environmental impact of diesel generator electricity supply. (Baseline)

Considering the continuous power available from the diesel generator (80 kW), taking into account the amount of time it worked (3.5 hours) and the GWP related to electricity generated through a diesel generator (0.793 kg of CO₂-eq/ kWh), the amount of CO₂ emitted through these operations is equal to 222 kg of CO₂-eq.

4.2.4.2. Scenario 2: Environmental impact of large-scale battery operation (INVADE)

If instead, the installed large-scale battery is used and supposing the electricity comes from the average Spanish grid, the 280 kWh needed by the critical building would have been responsible for 78.68 kg of CO₂-eq. Considering as well the environmental impact

of the manufacturing and usage of the battery, 15.52 kg of CO₂-eq have been emitted under this time-period.

Table 19: Results summary of the Spanish Pilot-site

	Grid mix [kg CO₂-eq]	Diesel generator [kg CO₂-eq]	CES [kg CO₂-eq]	Total GWP [kg CO₂-eq/year]
Scenario 1	-	222.00	-	222.02
Scenario 2	78.68	-	15.52	94.20

In short, 0 emissions cannot be achieved even installing CES, since even renewables resources have environmental impacts. However, by implementing the CES, 57.56 % of CO₂ can be achieved. Furthermore, in this scenario, the time period on which the battery was being charged was not considered. If the CES would have been charged during off-peak hours, where more renewable sources are used, a lower GWP value could have obtained.

4.2.5. German Pilot Site

The German Pilot Site is located in the area of Freiburg and is based on a hybrid approach. It focuses on both, building up one centralised energy storage device as well as examining new business models for distributed energy storage. For the aim of assessing the potential environmental impacts of the German pilot-site, only the DES case is taken into consideration.

- Decentralized Energy Storage (DES)

The connection of distributed energy storage is the second part of the hybrid pilot implementation in Germany. The German household battery market is the most advanced in Europe. There are already several hundred-battery storage installations of private individuals in the entire supply area of badenova. Under existing market conditions, these batteries can be connected and marketed as virtual power plants. However, this approach can even lead to additional network load if marketing does not take into account the capacity of the network.

Eleven customers who are owners of a house that is already equipped with PV systems and small batteries with individual capacities of around 10kWh have been contracted

and connected to the INVADE platform. The main objectives of this sub-pilot site are prosumer self-balancing and peak shaving from the DSO perspective.

Figure 18 shows the system boundaries before and after the application of the INVADE technologies and platform.

Figure 18: German Pilot-Site system boundaries.

4.2.5.1. German/Badenova electricity grid mix

Germany has a national electricity mix that relies on different sources. Lignite and hard coal with a share of 24.46% and 13.72%, respectively, were the most used fossil fuels. Wind farms had the highest share of renewable energy capacity in the country and a total share of 20.63%, as presented in *Table 20*. Nuclear still made regular contributions (13.64%), while solar (7.83%) and biomass (7.63%) power plants surpassed the use of natural gas (6.41%) in 2018. Hydropower accounted for just 2.81% of the total electricity production. The total electricity produced during the year in the country was equal to 2,184 TWh.

Table 20: Percentage of resources used in 2018 [52]

Lignite	Wind	Hard Coal	Nuclear	Solar	Biomass	Natural gas	Hydro	Others
24.42 %	20.63 %	13.72 %	13.64 %	7.83 %	7.63 %	6.41 %	2.81 %	2.91 %

By considering all the resources used in 2018, the carbon intensity of 1 kWh is equal to 0.476 kg of CO₂-eq. However, this pilot-site does not rely on the national grid mix but on the one provided by the sales and trading division of badenova. In this case, the electricity grid mix is shown in *Table 21*:

Table 21: Percentage of resources from Badenova Retailer. Provided by Badenova

Hydro	Wind Onshore	Wind Offshore	Nuclear	Solar	Biomass	Natural gas	Coal	Waste	Other Fuels
30.50 %	20.20 %	4.30 %	3.40 %	9.30 %	10.60 %	9.00 %	10.60 %	1.40 %	0.70 %

Considering the badenova electricity mix, the yearly average GWP value is 0.135 kg of CO₂-eq/kWh. As shown in *Table 22*, there is environmental impact reduction of 71% by using the electricity mix of badenova.

Table 22: Summary of results for German pilot-site

	GWP value [kg of CO ₂ -eq/kWh]
National mix	0.476
badenova mix	0.135

Table 22 clearly indicates that just by using another electricity mix itself, high environmental reductions in terms of CO₂ emissions can be achieved.

4.2.5.2. Home Energy Management System environmental savings

Scenario 1: Baseline

The pilot-site, as described in Figure 18, has 11 HEMS implemented, with PV panels and DES to increase self-consumption and decrease the overall consumption from the electricity grid. The period considered for the analysis accounts for one year. If all households had not installed a HEMS, the electricity provided by the HEMS would have been provided by the national electricity mix. By using the national electricity mix 91,550 kg of CO₂-eq would have been emitted.

Scenario 2: HEMS

Considering the 11 HEMS which have been installed in the pilot-sites a significant reduction of emitted O₂-eq can be observed. Considering the analyzed period of one year, 91,550 kg of CO₂-eq was avoided by consuming the locally produced energy instead of using the electricity mix from the grid. One should keep in mind that the environmental impact of manufacturing both, PV panels and DES, have to be included in the analysis.

The GWP value of polycrystalline PV modules manufacturing accounts to $72.14 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg of CO₂-eq/kWh; the GWP value of lithium-ion batteries accounts for $70.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg of CO₂-eq/kWh. In addition, the HEMS scenario considers locally produced electricity, but also electricity from the main grid being of 46,035.20 kWh/year. By using the GWP values for PV and battery manufacturing the overall emissions from the pilot site are calculated as shown in Table 23

Table 23: summary of results for Badenova pilot-site

	Grid mix GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq]	PV panels GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq]	DES GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq]	Total emissions [kg CO ₂ -eq/year]
Scenario 1: Grid	91,550.0	-	-	91,550.00
Scenario 2: HEMS	6,217.18	7,714.86	7,550.17	21,482.21

Table 23 shows that even by considering the environmental impacts of the PV panels manufacturing and use phase as well as the manufacturing and use phase of lithium-ion batteries, significant carbon intensity reductions of 76.5 % are achieved.

5. Conclusions

This document presents the final results of the Life Cycle Assessment under the INVADE H2020 Project, for all the pilot-sites under study. A common methodology has been defined, in order to assess the potential environmental impacts or savings due to the implementation of the INVADE concept and platform. Each pilot has supplied the available data from their pilot-sites in order to apply the LCA methodology defined in D3.4.

LCA methodology according to ISO Standards 14040 and 14044 has been implemented. More specifically, a new LCA methodology, the so-called peak-hourly LCA, to environmentally assess the greenhouse gas emissions of the electricity production on an hourly basis. Hence, it is key for the assessment of demand-response carbon footprint. Assumptions and hypotheses are important when defining the goal and scope of an LCA study since they could affect the results of the study. In this case, grid interconnections, network losses, and power plants' own consumption are not considered in the model. By considering them, even greater CO₂ savings could be achieved in some countries with the implementation of local flexibility markets.

The results of this study show that by considering the environmental impact of electricity generation, flexible resources such as EVs, water boilers, or batteries can be scheduled according to carbon intensity, reducing their environmental impacts, which is in line with the findings of Baumann et al. [55]. At present, DR strategies and flexibility services are implemented following price signals, for the purpose of achieving economic savings for the end-user. However, if decarbonization is the main objective of these initiatives, flexibility potential should be environmentally assessed. By implementing peak-shaving or load-shifting strategies from peak hours to off-peak hours, the flexibility potential can be quantified in CO₂ savings, using the maximum peak-hourly GWP value and the average GWP for the same functional unit. According to Table 10, the flexibility potential was around 16% in Bulgaria and Norway, greater than 5% in Germany and The Netherlands, and 21.3% in Spain, being the country with the maximum flexibility potential.

Using time-varying carbon prices based on temporal carbon intensity variations could be a good approach for designing carbon pricing strategies, enhancing the transition towards a low-carbon energy system. When defining and implementing DSM strategies, not only economic benefits should be considered, but also the environmental impacts

or savings thanks to load shifting and peak-shaving. Flexibility should be quantified in terms of carbon intensity since not all countries use the most polluting resources like natural gas or coal for covering peak-hours demand.

Table 24 shows a summary of results for each pilot site and scenario. However, it should be noticed that pilot-sites are not comparable between them since they have different nature and time horizons on which data have been collected. One important conclusion out of the deliverable is that, depending on the use case implemented, (self-balancing, congestion management, etc.), the environmental savings are significantly different. Also related to each pilot-site, the CO₂ savings due to flexibility services are strongly related to the main nature of the electricity grid mix for each country.

Table 24: Summary of results

		Total emissions [kg CO ₂ -eq]	Time period
Scenario 1: BAU	Norway	0.0287	N/A
	The Netherlands	631.40-1,060.50	1 year
	Bulgaria	110,392.17	1 month
	Spain	222.00	1 year
	Germany	91,550.00	1 year
Scenario 2: INVADE Concept	Norway	0.20844	N/A
	The Netherlands	158.71-252.49	1 year
	Bulgaria	108,847.71	1 month
	Spain	78.68	1 year
	Germany	21,482.21	1 year

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